

CHILD'S AGE AND PSYCHOLOGY IN PRIMARY GRADES CHARACTERISTICS

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Annotatsiya: Sizga taqdim etilyotgan maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini maktab hayotiga kirib kelishida psixologiyaning ahamiyati va maktabga jalb qilish va qiziqtirish ahamiyati haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bolalar, boshlang'ich, ota, ona, maktab, yosh, oila, psixologiya, sinf.

Аннотация: В представленной вам статье рассматривается значение психологии при вхождении младших школьников в школьную жизнь и важность привлечения и интереса к школе.

Ключевые слова: Дети, начальная школа, отец, мать, школа, возраст, семья, психология, класс.

Abstract: The article presented to you discusses the importance of psychology in the entry of elementary school students into school life and the importance of attracting and interesting to school.

Key words: Children, primary, father, mother, school, age, family, psychology, class.

The first and most important point in children's development is the beginning of school. Primary school age from 6-7 to 10-11 years is a certain period in the life of a child and his family.

The main task of parents is to prepare the child for school. Despite the desire to go to school, not all children are ready to study. Therefore, before admitting a

child to school, it is important that he/she (children) have an interview with the school psychologist.

When the child goes to school for the first time, the family experiences a certain crisis. At the beginning of the school period, a seven-year crisis occurs, which leads to a transition to a new social situation that requires a new content of relationships. Previous social relationships (kindergarten, etc.) have already ended, so he tends to go to school as soon as possible and enter into new social relationships.

The crisis process depends on when the child goes to school and how ready he is to learn. Also, teaching a child to read and write fluently at age 4 or 5 doesn't mean much yet, except, of course, for gifted children! If a child comes to school at the age of 7-8, he must go through certain stages, then the game no longer interests him as before, it fades into the background. The child tries to change the game, there is a desire for effective, meaningful activities that are valued by adults. A child begins to have a subjective desire to grow up.

First of all, negative symptoms directed at parents may appear. When the child comes to school, his emotional state stabilizes and internal comfort is restored. A seven-year-old child entering school is experiencing serious changes in life: mental, physical loads, emotional changes are increasing, the daily routine is changing, a number of new worries and obligations appear. Most seven-year-olds are ready for school, their memory is developed enough, they know how to manage their attention and have a rich vocabulary. A first-grader can perform elementary operations in his mind, understand what he hears, and manage his emotions and actions within a certain range. At the age of 6-3, other stages are noted in children who came to school early, in which the child is no longer engaged in studies, but in games, because for now it remains his leading activity. Necessary conditions for

the child to transition from play activities to education did not create. He continues to act out in class and at home, which leads to learning and behavior problems. The child experiences dissatisfaction with his social status, experiences emotional and personal discomfort. In behavior emerging negative symptoms are directed against parents and teachers.

It should be noted that establishing contact with children is a big task for the teacher himself. The child-teacher system begins to determine the child's relationship to both parents and children. Good grades and good behavior come from the teacher, and of course, relationships with peers and parents depend on the grades he gets.

Education and upbringing of a young student is his character, health and intellect to an individual approach to his personality, taking into account his abilities based on There may be arguments between parents about how to raise a student, how to react to grades, participation in school life, who will monitor and monitor the completion of homework, whether to give the child full education, etc. Such crises occur during family life, marriage, childbirth, first schooling, adolescence and young adulthood, and, of course, adulthood. Parents' task - If there are difficulties in raising a child, parents should ask for help from specialists (school psychologist, family psychologist, etc.) without fear or shame. A family psychologist shows and teaches ways and means to improve family relationships. Sometimes parents do not know how to identify relationships and how they can destroy the child's psyche.

Especially if the child witnesses the clarification of the relationship between the parents. This is another important point! A child should feel loved! A person needs unconditional acceptance and love throughout his life, which is very important for everyone to be successful, confident, harmoniously developed, but

this need is even more developed in children. At the primary school age, it becomes the basis for a comfortable personal development of the child in the future. The way to form a student's personality largely depends on how successful this stage of growth is.

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